

A GLANCE AT BOTIR ZOKIROV'S CREATION

Babanazarova G.Y.¹

Karshi State University

Teacher of the Faculty of Arts

Sultanov B.S.²

The leading teacher of the Karshi specialized art school

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7425963>

Annotation: Botir Karimovich Zokirov is a talented singer, translator, artist and actor who laid the foundation stone of Uzbek pop music in the 60 years of the XX century. His operas, arias, Uzbek folk songs, and foreign strokes were all over the world in their time and have not lost their significance to this day. In addition to national songs, the singer's repertoire includes songs in Italian, French, Spanish, Russian, Greek, Iranian, Arabic and Hindi.

Keywords: Variety, B.Zokirov, romance, opera, aria.

The People's Artist of Uzbekistan, Botir Karimovich Zokirov, a talented singer, translator, artist and actor who laid the foundation stone of pop music of Uzbekistan in the 60s of the 20th century. Botir Zokirov was born on April 26, 1936 in Moscow. He studied at the Vocal Faculty of the Tashkent State Conservatory (1952-57), the Directing Faculty of the Tashkent State Institute of Theater and Fine Arts (1958-62).

Speaking of Botir Zakirov, we cannot help but touch on his dynasty. Botir Zakirov was born into a family of artists, his father Karim Zakirov (1912-1977), the head of the dynasty, was a People's Artist of Uzbekistan, an actor, a skilled lapar performer. Luiza Zokirova, sister of B.Zokirov (born 1938 in Tashkent), is a pop singer. Brothers Nafval Zakirov (1941 Tashkent) pop singer, Farrukh Zokirov (1946 Tashkent) People's artist of Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Karakalpakstan, Tajikistan, pop singer, actor, composer, soloist of the Yalla group, Jamshid Zokirov (1948 Tashkent) Honored Artist of Uzbekistan. Batir Zakirov's children, Bakhtiyor (born 1962 in Tashkent) and Bakhodir Zakirov, are distinguished artists in Uzbekistan.

Since Botir Zakirov has a very impressive timbre and sweet voice, many composers have written songs and romances specifically for Botir Zakirov's voice (lyrical-dramatic tenor). In

addition, the singer performed the songs of the brotherly nations. Romances and songs of Uzbek composers play an important role in Honanda's work. Among them, M. Burkhanov's "Maftun boldim", "Namedonam chi nom dorad", I. Akbarov's "Yor kel", "Ra'no", "Gazli", "I remember you", Saifi Jalil's "Mad monologue", "Nights counting stars" and performer of other romances.

Barnolar ichra barno – Ra'no

Gulmisan, Gulyormisan,

Gulmisan, Gulyormisan?

Oshiqqa dildormisan?

Hamma gullardan a'lo Ra'no...

Hamma gullardan a'lo Ra'no,... **"Sadoiy"**

Also reworked in pop style from Indian songs "Nechun hayol chomding?", "Dream of the heart", "Melchale", from Iranian songs "Maro bebus", "Ayriliq", from Egyptian songs "Arabic tango", "Sleep thief", from Syrian songs "I cry to my past", "Beautiful girl" from Lebanese songs, Mexican "Goodbye love" and Italian "Long Live Love" were original performances.

In 1956, B.Zokirov established the youth ensemble "Yoshlik" and gained great fame. The operas, arias, Uzbek folk songs, and foreign hits that he sang spread all over the world in his time and have not lost their importance even today. In addition to national songs, Honanda's repertoire includes songs in Italian, French, Spanish, Russian, Greek, Iranian, Arabic, and Indian languages.

Because B.Zokirov was not only a singer but also an artist, his works as an artist are also very noteworthy. Honanda also performed melodious songs influenced by his drawings. In the last years of his life, B.Zokirov was seriously ill and suffered from this disease for several years, but he died on January 23, 1985 in Tashkent at the age of 48.

B.Zokirov also showed himself as a film actor. Multidisciplinary artist created images such as "When the Flowers Open", "Fiery Roads" by Rabindranath Tagore, "The Youth of a Genius" by Abdullah.

"Когда цветут розы" (1959)

"Когда цветут розы" (1959)

Today, there are many young people who are following in the footsteps of Botir Zakirov, besides, in their work, we can find a number of new directions and styles in Uzbek pop music (pop-rock, ethno-jazz, pop-jazz, disco, hip hop...) in the works of our young singers. . It is known that pop music is a new direction that has been seriously and scientifically studied in Uzbekistan since the years of independence. It is not an exaggeration to say that despite the fact that more than half a century has passed since the modern directions of this music have

been formed in Uzbekistan, the system of analyzing pop songs has not been established. Maybe that's why Botir Zakirov, the owner of a lively talent, the owner of a voice like his timbre, did not appear again.

In order to perpetuate the name of the founder of Uzbek pop music, one of the streets of Tashkent was named after him. In addition, the youth art center in Samarkand is named after him, the pop orchestra named after B.Zokirov was established in 1994, the B.Zokirov fund was established in 1995, since 1989, the competition of modern pop singers has been held in the name of B.Zokirov, 2020 is the year of Botir Zokirov The National Pop Art Institute was established. In addition, on April 20, 2017, at the National Library named after Alisher Navoi, the presentation of the book "*Storms of the Heart*" by journalist Ashurali Joraev, who served in the Republic of Uzbekistan, was held. Botir Zakirov's work has always interested us and served as an example for our youth. Currently, our musicologists are writing articles, dissertations, monographs about this artist and his dynasty.

By the decree of the former President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, Botir Zakirov was posthumously awarded the Order of Merit. Also, his greatest reward is the love of the whole nation and his eternal memory.

References:

- 1.National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, Tashkent., 2001.
- 2.Joraev Ashurali "*Storms of the Heart*" T., 2017.
- 3.Tursunova G.A. Candidate's dissertation entitled "*Karim Zakirov and his dynasty - in the section of the musical culture of Uzbekistan of the 20th century*".

